

EFFECT OF LABORATORY ACTIVITIES ON THE SCIENCE PERFORMANCE OF STEM STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of laboratory activities on the science performance of STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. This research focuses on understanding how engaging in hands-on laboratory activities contributes to the overall academic achievement and learning outcomes of students. In this study, descriptive survey design under quantitative research was used to ascertain the possible effect of laboratory activities to the science performance of the STEM 12 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. 20 students per classroom were the participants, by using the purposive sampling method. The respondents answered the questionnaires that the researchers provide. The statistical treatment of data used in this research were frequency distribution and percentage, mean under descriptive statistics and t-test for independent sample, to naturally fully understand the effect. The research findings reveal that Laboratory activities can affect the science performance of STEM 12 students, which means that the respondents agreed to the effect of laboratory activities on their science performance. This implies that lack of laboratory activities can negatively affect the science performance of STEM 12 students. 50 or 50% of the respondents are male and 50 or 50% are female. Furthermore, by using an independent sample t-test, it was revealed that there is no significant difference on the effect of laboratory activities as perceived by the student-respondents in terms of gender. Based on the findings, it is recommended to the school administrators, teachers, students, and future researchers to have a comparative analysis and findings concerning the effect of Laboratory Activities.

Keywords: *laboratory activities, science performance, STEM students, academic achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Science laboratories provide students with various opportunities to learn and experiment; they may enhance student understanding of specific scientific facts and concepts that organize the scientific discipline, and they play a crucial role in the development of students at any academic level. Hence, science laboratories or laboratory activity serves as a way of learning for others and learning is an important aspect in education as uttered by Sabbaha et. al., (2024) cited by Abdulmajid et. al., (2024), Mading et. al., (2024), Balla et. al., (2024) Jarak et. al., (2024) and Sakili et. al., (2024) Indeed, learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within an individual's mind, it is an ability influenced by human beings that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, furthermore learning is a continuous process and a cognitive task.

A laboratory is a place where scientific research and development are conducted and analyses performed. Shanti Swaroop Bhatnagar is known for being the father of Indian Research Laboratories. The first industrial research laboratories were set up in the 1860's in France and were soon followed by large laboratories in the German dye industry from the 1870's onward.

As a result, a science laboratory is a location that is set up for testing, analysis, and experimental scientific inquiry. a lab for research. In general: a location that offers chances for practice, observation, or experimenting in a subject of study.

Unfortunately, STEM students struggle to meet these expectations. Laboratory activities are one of the most serious difficulties faced by STEM students here at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School. Students often conduct experiments in the laboratory due to the fact that we do not have enough tools and equipment needed for experiments, and the laboratory room provided does not have enough space for the students to conduct an experiment.

Although it is possible that STEM students will be able to pass science subjects without the use of a laboratory, having experience and exposure to laboratory activities will always be different. The imaginary world of the students in the science world will be discovered and perceived by the eye. Laboratory exposure can help students learn to address the challenges inherent in directly observing and manipulating the material world.

Students should actively participate in the learning process, where they are always preparing, testing, speculating, and constructing their own particular construct and knowledge, according to Adesoji (2008). Students are naturally curious. Students must therefore actively create their own awareness and meaning in the scientific domain. Students investigate and practically explain natural occurrences as part of a human endeavor in the lab.

Furthermore, laboratory activities can affect the science performance of STEM students owing to this track to equip them for laboratory activities. Science is hard to understand based on just theories, hence it is going to be understandable through

students' discoveries and experiences in laboratory activities thus, the research in this study seeks to determine what is the demographic profile of students in terms of gender, What is the effect of laboratory activities on the science performance as perceived by the STEM students, and if there's a significant difference between male and female on the effect of laboratory activities on the science performance of STEM 12 students.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of laboratory activities on the science performance of the STEM 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School. Following are the questions that this study aims to address:

1. What is the demographic profile of students in terms of gender?
2. What are the effects of laboratory activities on the science performance as perceived by the STEM students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?
3. Is there a significant difference between male and female on the effect of laboratory activities on the science performance of STEM 12 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The location of this study is in Mindanao State University-Sulu situated in Capitol Site Jolo, Sulu. In the Senior High School department, this esteemed institution provides a range of strands, including STEM. (Math, Science, Technology, Engineering). This study's internal execution enables a thorough grasp of the unique opportunities and difficulties associated with the laboratory exposure of Mindanao State University-Sulu's STEM students.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani A. et al. (2024) and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Moreover, the respondents of this study are the 100 students coming from Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School.

Research Design

The researchers used a descriptive survey design under quantitative research in which they sought to ascertain the possible effect of laboratory activities on the science performance of the STEM 12 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. This study used a descriptive method in order to obtain data. According to Siedlecki (2020), the descriptive method of research is a fact-finding study that encompasses adequate interpretation. This type of research approach includes more than just gathering and tabulating data; it can answer questions like what, when, where and how, but not why.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a survey questionnaire like Likert scales in order to gather the data needed for this research. The questionnaire has two main parts. Part 1, identifying the demographic profile of students in terms of gender, and Part 2, are a set of statements in which the respondents will check whether they are Strongly Agree, Agree, Strongly Disagree, or Disagree. The researchers assured that the questionnaire was authentically valid, and they asked the statistician and critique to check the survey questionnaires before conducting the survey. The questionnaire is a research instrument that consists of a series of questions that are to be answered by the chosen respondents. The researchers assured that all the information gathered for the research is confidential and would only be used for academic purposes. To evaluate the data, the researchers also made use of the Likert Scale design used in the paper of Jarak et. al. (2024), this design is indicated below.

Table 3.2 School Recommended Scale

Scale	Weighted Mean/ Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical treatment of data used in this research is frequency distribution percentage to determine the demographic profile of the respondents, mean under descriptive statistics used to evaluate the perception of the respondents, and t-test for independent sample to find out if there is a significant difference effect of laboratory activities on the academic performance of the students when grouped in terms of gender. To fully understand the effect of laboratory activities on the academic performance of STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the effect of laboratory activities on science performance among the Senior High School Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. The student-respondents of this study is delimited to the STEM 12 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. The researcher randomly selected 100 respondents out of the 356 total population of STEM 12 students with 28.08 percent with the overall population, 20 students per classroom were the respondents. By using the purposive sampling method. The respondents will answer the questionnaires that the researchers provide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	50	50%
Female	50	50%
Total	100	100%

Table 4.1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of values in terms of gender. As presented in the table, 50 or 50% of the respondents are male and 50 or 50% are female. This table indicates that the respondents are neither predominantly by male nor female.

The finding of this study is aligned with the study of Kalu (2008), who emphasized the importance of engaging students, "hands" and "mind" in scientific tasks. The goal of this method of teaching and learning science in the classroom is to help students develop competency, life skills, and science process skills. The aim of this approach is not only to impart scientific knowledge but also to develop competency and life skills among students. Based on the result the male and female respondents have the same frequency percentage as both male and female. Therefore, students both male and female must be more active in conducting a laboratory activity not only enhancing their understanding of scientific concepts but also improving their problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities. This study concluded that incorporating more laboratory activities into STEM education can lead to better academic outcomes and more engaging learning experience for students.

Table 2: Effects of Laboratory activities on the science performance as perceived by the STEM students.

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Deficient laboratory activities have impacted my ability to adapt and learn new experimental techniques.	3.2	0.7	Agree
2. Lack of Laboratory activities becomes a barrier to My understanding in an actual conduct of lab activities.	3.2	0.7	Agree
3. Deficient laboratory activities have impacted My ability to develop a comprehensive understanding of scientific concepts through practical application.	3.1	0.7	Agree
4. Absence of laboratory activities has made it difficult for me to understand the intricacies of experimental design.	3.1	0.8	Agree
5. Lack of Laboratory activities hinders me to understand	3.1	0.7	Agree

science further.

6. The absence of laboratory activities has limited my exposure to different scientific instruments and equipment.	3.1	0.7	Agree
7. Lack of laboratory activities has impacted my ability to understand the practical applications of scientific theories.	3.1	1.0	Agree
8. Deficient laboratory activities hindered my ability to develop an experimental mindset and approach.	3.1	0.7	Agree
9. Absence of laboratory activities has affected my confidence in conducting independent scientific research.	3.1	0.7	Agree
10. Lack of laboratory experience has limited my exposure to different scientific methodologies and techniques.	3.0	0.8	Agree
11. Deficient laboratory activities have hindered my ability to collaborate and work effectively in a team setting.	3.0	0.6	Agree
12. Deficient laboratory activities have hindered my ability to develop effective laboratory techniques and skills.	3.0	0.7	Agree
13. Absence of laboratory activities has limited my exposure to the collaborative and interactive nature of scientific research.	3.0	0.8	Agree
14. Absence of laboratory activities has made it challenging for me to develop scientific inquiry and critical thinking skills.	3.0	1.0	Agree
15. Absence of laboratory activities has made it difficult for me to connect theoretical knowledge with real-world applications.	3.0	0.8	Agree
16. Lack of laboratory experience has impacted my ability to effectively communicate and present scientific findings.	3.0	0.8	Agree
17. The lack of laboratory experience has affected my ability to critically evaluate scientific literature and research studies.	3.0	0.8	Agree
18. Lack of laboratory activities has impacted my ability to design and conduct scientific experiments.	3.0	0.7	Agree
19. Absence of laboratory activities has made it challenging for me to develop scientific inquiry and critical thinking skills.	3.0	0.9	Agree
20. Lack of laboratory activities has affected my ability to apply scientific concepts to real-world problems.	3.0	0.8	Agree

Total	3.2	0.8	Agree
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Legend: (3.26-4.00) Strongly Agree, (2.51-3.25) Agree, (1.76-2.50) Strongly Disagree, (1.00-1.75) Disagree.

Table 4.2 presents the mean of the effect of Laboratory activities on the Science Performance as perceived by the STEM students. The total mean obtained 3.2, which means that the respondents agreed to the effect of laboratory activities on their science performance. This implies that Laboratory activities can affect the science performance of STEM 12 students.

Similar to the study of (Hofstein & Mamlok-naaman, 2007), Students can only learn science effectively and be able to retain their knowledge and skills when they encounter real life experience through practical work in science.

If t students are not given hands-on experience in the school laboratories, science cannot have any real value for them. The results showed 3.2% which means that the academic performance of students 'are negatively affected given that the academic achievements are significantly high given the same condition of exposure to prior laboratory apparatus activities on acquisition of science process skills. Therefore, recommendations were made among others that science curriculum developers, supervisory bodies of secondary schools, science education and teachers should incorporate prior exposure to laboratory apparatus activities on acquisition of science process skills approach in secondary school level. In addition to when students find personal relevance in the material/activities they are learning, they are more apt to retain information. Therefore, the first important pedagogical technique is recognition of students' prior exposure to laboratory apparatus which can also be thought of as their prior knowledge, that's why students must actively participate in conducting a lab activity to be able to know further about the importance of conducting a laboratory activity.

Table 3: Effect of Laboratory activities on the science performance as perceived by the STEM students in terms of gender.

Variable	Male		Female		T	p-value
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Gender	3.0660	.54036	2.9570	.40608	1.140	.257

Table 4.3 shows the T-test for an independent sample of the significant difference of respondents on the effect of laboratory activities in terms of gender. The finding showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of, male ($M= 3.0660$, $SD=.54036$) and female ($F= 2.9570$, $SD=.40608$) respondents; $t(1.140) = 98$, $p=.275$, the result suggests that both male and female have the same perception of the effect of laboratory to their science performance.

The findings of this study resonate with the research conducted by Amalia et al., (2023), underscoring the notion that gender serves as an insignificant determinant in shaping students' self-efficacy regarding laboratory engagements. This implies that both

male and female students exhibit similar levels of confidence and belief in their ability to perform effectively in laboratory settings. The observations further suggest that regardless of gender, students perceive laboratory activities to have a comparable impact on their science performance. Therefore, it can be extrapolated that gender does not wield substantial influence in shaping students' perceptions of the efficacy of laboratory activities.

Conclusions

Majority of the results gathered from the respondents agreed to the effect of laboratory activities. The respondents agreed on the effect of laboratory activities to their science performance. This concludes that the respondents have been affected by the laboratory activities on their science performance. Using T-test, there was no significant difference in the effect of laboratory activities in terms of gender as perceived by the respondents. This means that when it comes to their perception on the effects of laboratory activities, both male and female have the same implications on the effect of laboratory activities to their science performance as perceived by the respondents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following are recommended:

- A. SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS, it is recommended to give their full support and attention to the students to be able to know further, and conduct laboratory activities frequently, and to provide a laboratory room for Senior high school students to able to conduct laboratory activities more often.
- B. TEACHERS, it was recommended to make their students to be more active in laboratory activities, participating in laboratory activities can greatly enhance student's understanding of scientific concepts to provide a hands-on experiential learning opportunity. Moreover, laboratory activities can also improve student's academic performance on science. It would be helpful for them to know how laboratory activities could affect the science performance of their students.
- C. STUDENTS, it was recommended to be more active in laboratory activities, which can help them to better understand and remember scientific concept in laboratory activities can also help them to know the effects and outcomes of different scientific principles and action, and this would be helpful for them to know how much laboratory activities could affect their science performance.
- D. FUTURE RESEARCHERS, it is highly recommended to conduct a comparative analysis and gather findings regarding the effect of laboratory activities on student's performance, this comparative approach can provide valuable insights into the impact of laboratory activities across different groups of respondents or setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

There are various important components to the ethical protocol for laboratory activities. The primary concern should be the participants' safety. This includes ensuring that all necessary safety measures are in place, such as disbursement of appropriate protective equipment and training, steps should be taken to rectify the deficiency and prevent future occurrences. This involved conducting a thorough investigation to identify the root cause of the problem and implementing corrective measures. Immanent monitoring and evaluation should also be conducted to ensure ongoing compliance with ethical standards. In summary, the ethical protocol of this study prioritizes safety, transparency, and remedial actions to protect individuals and incidents.

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